

IDENTIFYING GLOBAL CO-OCCURRENCE OF HYDROLOGICAL, METEOROLOGICAL AND AGRICULTURAL DROUGHTS

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Abstract

Droughts affect more people around the world than any other natural hazard. Lower than average precipitation is the usual reason leading to drought, but other drivers, such as increased evaporation, can also have a large influence on drought development. Climate change has also been predicted to intensify drought severity and frequency in the future. Traditionally, droughts have been divided into four broad categories: socio-economic, meteorological, agricultural, and hydrological. These different drought-types often co-occur, and there are numerous indices aiming to quantify the severity, intensity, and duration related to the different drought categories. This proof-of-concept study aims to estimate drought severity, duration and intensity globally at 0.25°x0.25° resolution for the years 2004-2011 with ten different drought indices utilizing data from the Earth System Data Lab. Our results confirm the expectation that different drought types do often co-occur, however there are differences depending on the indices used for the drought types. For example, agricultural drought co-occurs with hydrological drought in 40% of events, and meteorological drought will develop into a hydrological drought in 50% of the events. This information can be useful e.g. when setting up early warning systems. The chosen drought indices are also sufficiently diverse to measure different aspects of drought characteristics and types. The study is reproducible in the Earth System Data Lab system by cloning and running the Jupyter Notebooks in git repository <https://version.aalto.fi/gitlab/wdrg/esdl--drought-co-occurrence>.

Introduction

Droughts are defined as a temporary state of water deficit (Dracup et al. 1980), and they affect more people than any other natural hazard (Kallis 2008). They often result from decreased precipitation - however, other drivers, such as increased evaporation, can also lead to the development of droughts (Sheffield et al. 2011). During the 20th century, severe droughts led to deaths and economic damages counted in millions and billions, respectively (Sheffield et al. 2011, Dai 2011a). Because of climate change, droughts have been predicted to intensify in the future, which would increase the extent of their impacts as well (Dai 2011b).

Generally, droughts have been divided into four broad categories: meteorological, agricultural, hydrological, and socio-economic (Sheffield et al. 2011). Definitions of different drought types are diverse, dependent on the disciplinary perspective and region, and there is no universal definition (Wilhite and Glantz 1985). Here, we broadly define the four drought types using Wilhite and Glantz's (1985) analysis of over 150 published definitions. The most prevalent drought, meteorological drought, refers to insufficient rainfall, as relating to a regional 'norm'. Agricultural drought links meteorological drought to its agricultural impacts, including crop evapotranspiration. Hydrological drought is concerned with the effects of dry spells on surface and ground water bodies. Finally, socio-economic drought is used to express the social and economic effects of the previous three drought types (ibid.).

The categorization is not clear-cut, as the different drought types are related to each other and can co-occur. For example, a prolonged meteorological drought can lead to an agricultural drought, when soil moisture is affected. If the water deficit leads to lower levels of groundwater levels and/or smaller streamflows, the drought can be defined as hydrological. All droughts that impact human activities can be called socio-economic (Kallis 2008). The impacts of droughts can be challenging to assess, since they depend strongly on the normally prevalent hydrological status (i.e. hazard potential) as well as socio-economic processes (i.e. vulnerability and exposure (IPCC 2014)) in the drought area.

The development of droughts is a slow and cumulative process, and can be very difficult to identify at first. Therefore, deeper understanding how different drought types are related both spatially and temporally can help to improve drought preparedness, mitigation and action plans. To illustrate with an example: if agricultural drought always co-occurs with hydrological drought, increasing surface water irrigation infrastructure may not be an efficient solution for drought preparedness and could spell disaster to downstream communities. However, if the river system is large enough, streamflow may not be substantially affected if precipitation in upstream reaches is at normal levels.

Our study aims to find correlation and interlinkages between different drought types and drought characteristics (i.e. severity, duration, intensity and area). Deeper understanding about drought types and characteristics and their interlinkages are important when determining the impact of drought and trying to improve resilience against drought. To attain more knowledge, we compute ten drought indices using data from the Earth System Data Lab (ESDL), and perform statistical analysis of co-occurrence of drought types and drought characteristics. There is a large body of literature on droughts, but to our knowledge, global analysis of this type has not been conducted before, especially given the high spatial resolution (global, 0.25°x0.25°) of the ESDL data.

This report accompanies a Jupyter Notebook(s) which can be used to replicate the main findings and provides additional visualizations. The git repository containing this report, and required data for replication of this study can be found in <https://version.aalto.fi/gitlab/wdrg/esdl--drought-co-occurrence>.

Methods and data

Data

The Earth System Data Lab is a joint effort by the European Space Agency, Max Planck Institute for Biogeochemistry, and Brockmann Consult GmbH to facilitate research about the relationships between the atmosphere, biosphere and society. For facilitating the research, the Earth System Data Cube (ESDC) was developed. The ESDC provides analysis-ready data for tens of biophysical variables, which can be accessed and analysed remotely on a cloud server. In this study, we utilize five of these variables, namely precipitation, potential evaporation, transpiration, soil moisture, and fAPAR (fraction of absorbed photosynthetically active radiation). An external dataset, Linear Optimal Runoff Aggregate (LORA v1.0, Hobeichi et al. 2019), was used to estimate hydrological droughts.

Methods

Drought indices

Prior to assessing the co-occurrence of different drought types, we calculated ten drought indices from the ESDC raw data and two external data products. The ten indices with the corresponding input parameters are presented in Table 1. fAPAR and soil moisture were utilized to identify agricultural drought. fAPAR is derived from satellite observations, and it represents the fraction of solar radiation that is absorbed by plants for photosynthesis. While fAPAR relates directly to plant health, soil moisture provides information about the plants growing conditions and can inform whether plants suffer from water stress. Both fAPAR and soil moisture data were processed into monthly standardized anomalies (z-score) by subtracting the monthly means and dividing with the respective standard deviations.

Table 1. Used drought indices. (Drought type abbreviations: met=meteorological, agri=agricultural, hyd = hydrological and socio-eco=socio-economical).

Full name	Drought type	Input parameters
Standardised Precipitation Index (SPI3 and SPI12)	Met, agri, hyd and socio-eco	Precipitation
Standardised Precipitation- Evapotranspiration Index (SPEI3 and SPEI12)	Met, agri, hyd and socio-eco	Precipitation - Pot. Evap.transpiration
Standardised Runoff Index (SRI3 and SRI12)	Agri, hyd	Runoff (external)
Standardised Streamflow Index (SSI3 and SSI12)	Hyd, socio-eco	Streamflow (external)
Standardised Soil moisture Anomaly Index (SMDI)	Agri	Soil moisture
Fraction of Absorbed Photosynthetically Active Radiation Anomaly index (fAPAR anomaly)	Agri	Fraction of Absorbed Photosynthetically Active Radiation

Standardized Precipitation Index (SPI) and Standardized Precipitation Evapotranspiration Index (SPEI) are widely used drought indices. They solely use precipitation (SPI) or the difference between precipitation and potential evapotranspiration (SPEI) to calculate a probability for precipitation of any magnitude in a given location. Generally, in SPI and SPEI probabilities can be calculated for any number of timescales from 1 month to 48 months or even longer. In this study we used a 3-month SPI and SPEI for seasonal (meteorological) drought identification and a 12-month index for annual (agricultural, hydrological and socio-economical droughts) anomaly detection.

To compare across different indices, the values were standardized. The SPI and SPEI values were obtained by fitting the values into a gamma distribution, while soil moisture and fAPAR anomalies were assumed to follow a normal distribution. Figure 1 provides information about how the standardized scores relate to probabilities.

Figure 1. Indicator classification in relation to the normal curve. The percentages present the probability of that class, not the cumulative probability. Adapted from Keyantash 2018.

Standardized runoff and streamflow drought indices (SRI and SSI, respectively) were estimated by first downscaling runoff to HydroBASINS level 8 catchments (approx. 700 km², Lehner and Grill, 2013) followed by rasterization to 0.25° grid (cell resolution approx. 775 km² at equator) using bilinear interpolation. Downscaling runoff and routing for streamflow estimation was performed with hydrostreamer R package (Kallio, 2018) externally. The finished runoff and streamflow data were imported to the ESDL system via a git repository, after which SRI and SSI were calculated similarly to SPI and SPEI.

Run theory

Droughts have traditionally been classified to four main categories: meteorological, hydrological, agricultural and socio-economic. In addition to the broad categories explained above, droughts also have other characteristics – duration, area, intensity and severity (Figure 2) – which can be estimated with run theory (Yevjevich 1967). The threshold for drought used in this study was ‘-1’ for all the indices.

Figure 2. Drought characteristics based on run theory. Adapted from Yevjevich (1967).

Spatial co-occurrence

We analyse the co-occurrence of drought events with two different definitions: 1) a temporal cell-by-cell analysis, where each 0.25° grid cell is analysed separately for drought characteristics (drought events lasting only one month were omitted); 2) a spatial analysis, where contiguous areas are interpreted as a single drought event (drought events which cover less than 3 grid cells were omitted), and temporal independence is assumed (i.e. temporal drought characteristics are not considered). The second definition is used for association rule analysis. Co-occurrence for the cell-by-cell analysis is straight forward: drought types co-occur if they are identified at the same location at the same time (same X- and Y- coordinates, same timestep). Co-occurrence for the contiguous drought event type is defined as: events co-occur if they overlap in at least two 0.25° grid cells, or if at least 50% of cells from either type under comparison intersect.

Association rules

Association rules are a type of data mining method which allows for analysing frequencies of categorical data and association between the categories (Aggarwal, 2015). Association rules are well suited for this type of analysis; it allows us to generate rules of the type $A \Rightarrow B$, which means that if an event of type A occurs, we also find event type B. The rules are inferred from a list of “transactions” (the term originates from the first applications of association rules to market basket analysis), which are given as a table with transactions as rows, and items as columns. If a transaction contains events of type A, and B, but not C, the transaction row sets to $\{TRUE, TRUE, FALSE\}$.

The degree of association for a given rule is expressed with support, confidence, and lift. Support describes the fraction of transactions which contain the items in the rule. Confidence of a rule describes the conditional probability of a transaction containing event type B, if event type A is contained in the transaction. Lift describes the “importance” of the rule: Lift values around 1 mean that the rule may not be useful in predicting B, on the condition of A, whereas a high lift value results in useful associations between event types. In this study, we only consider rules which have minimum support of 10%, and minimum confidence of 30%.

Results

Drought characteristics

Globally, the cell-by-cell analysis of drought types produced all together almost 6.2 million drought events, with drought type breakdown given in Table 2 ranging from a bit less than 400,000 (SRI12) to nearly a million (SPI3). The drought categories can be grouped into 5 groups of two, based on their drought characteristics; {fAPAR, SMDI}, {SPEI12, SPI12}, {SPEI3, SPI3}, {SRI12, SSI12} and {SRI3, SSI3}. These groups exhibit very similar properties in their event duration, intensity and severity, as can be seen from Table 3. As may be expected, duration and severity of drought events follow the length of period each drought index considers; highest mean durations and severities are found with 12-month indices, and shortest and least severe are the agricultural drought indices fAPAR and SMDI considering only 1 month. Mean intensities for all indices are very close to each other – this is likely due to fitting probability distribution using only 10 years of data and using it for the analysis.

Table 2. Number of drought events identified globally with the cell-by-cell analysis, between January 2004 to December 2012. For each drought index, mean event duration, intensity and severity are shown.

Drought Index	n	Mean Duration	Mean Intensity	Mean Severity
fAPAR	619,586	2.8	1.4	4.0
SMDI	560,100	2.7	1.5	4.0
SPEI12	558,618	5.7	1.3	8.1
SPI12	899,846	6.2	1.4	9.3
SPEI3	578,430	3	1.4	4.3
SPI3	978,153	3.3	1.4	4.9
SRI12	383,269	6.8	1.3	9.6
SSI12	607,386	6.8	1.3	9.6
SRI3	386,418	3.5	1.4	5.2
SSI3	616,276	3.6	1.4	5.2

Association between drought types

The drought co-occurrence definition based on spatially contiguous areas under drought produces a total of 600 thousand distinct drought events, globally. Each event is a transaction input for association rule mining which may contain several drought types. Table 3 gives the percentage of pairwise drought type occurrence from the total transaction count. fAPAR, SMDI, SPEI and SPI indices occur all in approximately 30% of the entire drought event dataset, while SRI and SSI indices occur 43-48% of all events. The 5% difference in occurrence of SSI and SRI suggest that river systems are more robust against streamflow driven, than they are to runoff driven hydrological drought events. In other words, headwater streams maybe more susceptible to droughts than streams with a considerable upstream contributing area. Overall, SPI/SPEI indices are fewer in number (mean number of events at any timestep 291-406 versus 721-1033 in other indices), but occur in larger areas than the other indices (95-162 vs. 22-42).

A χ^2 test was performed to test the assumption that the drought indices are related, resulting in a conclusion that there is a relationship between all indices, with SMDI and SSI12 being a border case (χ^2 statistic 3.92, p-value 0.05). This is logical, since streamflow may be at normal levels due to its dependency on upstream while at the same location soil moisture is under drought conditions.

Table 3. Pairwise occurrence in the drought event data given in percentages from the total number of identified events.

	fAPAR	SMDI	SPEI12	SPEI3	SPI12	SPI3	SRI12	SRI3	SSI12	SSI3
fAPAR	30.1	11.6	11.6	10.2	12.1	11.5	13.0	13.0	12.1	12.2
SMDI	11.6	31.7	13.3	12.7	13.7	13.9	14.7	14.6	13.6	13.5
SPEI12	11.6	13.3	31.5	17.1	25.0	17.2	14.0	14.3	12.8	13.1
SPEI3	10.2	12.7	17.1	29.4	15.6	22.4	13.7	13.7	12.6	12.7
SPI12	12.1	13.7	25.0	15.6	31.3	17.7	14.4	14.8	13.1	13.6
SPI3	11.5	13.9	17.2	22.4	17.7	29.6	14.0	14.0	12.9	12.9
SRI12	13.0	14.7	14.0	13.7	14.4	14.0	48.1	29.8	40.6	27.1
SRI3	13.0	14.6	14.3	13.7	14.8	14.0	29.8	48.7	27.1	41.1
SSI12	12.1	13.6	12.8	12.6	13.1	12.9	40.6	27.1	43.2	26.1
SSI3	12.2	13.5	13.1	12.7	13.6	12.9	27.1	41.1	26.1	43.9

The similarity between drought indices were also estimated with Jaccard coefficient. The results in Table 4 show that the similarities mostly lie between 0.05 and 0.3 with high similarities found in closely related indices. The similarity is especially high between 3- and 12-month indicators of the same index type. SRI and SSI indices have jaccard index of 0.8, highest of all. This is potentially because for headwater locations of rivers, runoff and streamflow are identical (there are no upstream areas which would contribute to streamflow in addition to the local runoff). Similarly, SPI and SPEI are closely related as both are driven by precipitation. Curiously, although Jaccard coefficient between SSI12 and fAPAR and SMDI are approximately similar, χ^2 test statistic shows a much higher degree of confidence in the relationship between SSI12 and fAPAR than SSI12 and SMDI (test statistic 983 and 3.92, respectively). Overall, the chosen indices measure sufficiently different aspects of drought to be meaningful.

Table 4. Pairwise Jaccard similarity between events identified by different indices.

	fAPAR	SMDI	SPEI12	SPEI3	SPI12	SPI3	SRI12	SRI3	SSI12	SSI3
fAPAR	1.00	0.23	0.24	0.22	0.26	0.25	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04
SMDI	0.23	1.00	0.28	0.28	0.29	0.31	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05
SPEI12	0.24	0.28	1.00	0.43	0.69	0.42	0.06	0.05	0.06	0.05
SPEI3	0.22	0.28	0.43	1.00	0.38	0.63	0.06	0.05	0.06	0.05
SPI12	0.26	0.29	0.69	0.38	1.00	0.44	0.06	0.05	0.06	0.05
SPI3	0.25	0.31	0.42	0.63	0.44	1.00	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05
SRI12	0.04	0.05	0.06	0.06	0.06	0.05	1.00	0.45	0.81	0.42
SRI3	0.04	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.45	1.00	0.42	0.80
SSI12	0.04	0.05	0.06	0.06	0.06	0.05	0.81	0.42	1.00	0.43
SSI3	0.04	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.42	0.80	0.43	1.00

Association rule mining with apriori-algorithm results in 186 rules, with the majority of them being somewhat redundant. Highest lift (importance) values were found in rules of containing three or four drought indices co-occurring together. Some interesting rules were found. Agricultural drought measured by SMDI or fAPAR co-occur with hydrological drought (SSI) approximately 40% of time with support of 13.6% and 12.1% and confidence of 43.1% and 40.1%. The results also indicate that meteorological droughts develop into hydrological droughts around 50% of the time. Long term

drought indices for hydrological and socio-economic droughts (12-month SPI, SPEI, SRI, SSI) occur together in 10% of drought events, and have more than 90% confidence if at least 3 of them are co-occurring in an event. The full list of association rules can be obtained by running the Jupyter Notebooks within the ESDL system.

Discussion and conclusions

The main findings from our results indicate that different drought types do indeed often co-occur. For example, it is shown that agricultural drought co-occurs with hydrological drought 40% of the time, which implies that utilizing irrigation water from streamflow may not always be a feasible option for drought mitigation. Further, our results show that a meteorological drought will develop into a hydrological drought around 50% of the time, which can be very useful for setting up early warning systems and for mitigation.

Further, our results show that the indices to describe similar drought types (e.g. SSI12 and SRI12) also provide similar results in terms of drought duration, severity and intensity. This information can potentially be useful for selecting appropriate indices for drought monitoring. However, it should be noted that although the drought characteristic information obtained here is valuable when comparing different drought events and evaluating potential socioeconomic impacts, similar values in different places are not necessarily comparable, since some areas are more vulnerable to drought than others.

The main limitation of this study is its relatively short time span. To account for natural variation in dry and wet spells, the interval used to calibrate drought indices should be at least 20 years and optimally even longer (WMO & GWP 2016). However, due to limitations in the ESDC data (PE and T data start in year 2003), only 10 years (2004-2013 for ESDC, and 2001-2010 for runoff and streamflow) of data was used for both calibrations. For the analysis, we used 8 years of data due to partly non-overlapping timeseries. Using a timeseries this short for calibrating the drought indices biases the results in some areas – e.g. if a multi-year drought has occurred during the calibration period. In addition, the mean drought intensities in the 8 years of analysis are nearly identical due because it is only slightly shorter than the 10-year calibration period, and it being fitted to a distribution.

Another important source of uncertainty related to the data is that the temporal resolution in the ESDC is mostly eight days. This is especially problematic for P and PET data, as they can have large temporal variability, which means that using temporally coarse data may not provide a reliable picture of real P and ET anomalies. Finally, fAPAR and soil moisture data do not cover the whole globe in the ESDC, and they were therefore interpolated, which also provides some additional uncertainty to the results.

To obtain more reliable results, it would be vital to increase the temporal resolution and length of the time series in follow-up studies, and to develop and extend the analysis and visualizations. Further, additional drought indices, such as Palmer Drought Severity Index or NDVI, could also be used to compare against, which would increase the robustness of the analyses.

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